

GENDER TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

D.Tursunova

Preschool education teacher of the department

M.Aminjonova

Preschool education 1st stage student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10279740>

Abstract: In the article, guarantees of gender equality have been created in the new Uzbekistan, this issue has been raised to the level of state policy and our country has taken a progressive step in the field of human rights, increasing the socio-political activity of women in our country, protecting their health, supporting their aspirations and initiatives, and providing them with decent work. and it is thought that special attention is paid to the creation of living conditions.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, democratic values, gender equality, women, social life, women's rights, women's protection.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, on the basis of the gender approach, scientific research works are being carried out in such directions as improving the quality of teaching in continuing education institutions, developing the social activity of women, and gender issues in professional education. According to the scientists of our republic, the process of developing gender aspects and the principles of implementation in the training of teachers is the main stage that brings them to the final result. A teacher who understands gender aspects can enable the young generation to think and act consciously through awareness and sensitivity to gender issues. Therefore, the movement to implement gender equality in education should begin with the teacher and cover his entire activity, from the stage of professional preparation to the stage of continuous professional development. Therefore, in addition to professional knowledge and skills, it is very important to train students in higher education institutions to develop important life skills, including analytical and critical thinking skills, problem solving, flexibility, interpersonal communication skills, as well as training them to work independently and cooperatively. . For this, it is necessary to implement a gender approach to the higher education system and develop effective mechanisms for its management.

The Berlin Communiqué (2003) states that the need to increase the competitiveness of education in order to strengthen social cohesion at the national and European levels and reduce social and gender inequality should be balanced with the improvement of the social description of European higher education.

The training of competent personnel that ensures the application of gender-sensitive practices and the principles of non-discrimination is carried out by introducing gender knowledge into the education system.

Gender mainstreaming in education is not only a matter of desire and quality, but also a legal obligation of the education system. For example, in Sweden, the Discrimination Act (2008) was adopted, according to which employers and educational institutions are obliged to

take active measures to promote gender equality, for example, to include specific goals, to take measures to prevent harassment.

Through education, ideas of tolerance for cultural, political, ethnic, religious and gender diversity are formed in the society. Often the debate about gender equality in education is limited to the discussion of gender priority: for example, if boys and girls are given the opportunity to study for higher education, then gender equality in education is considered to be achieved. However, ensuring gender equality in education is a broader concept than ensuring gender priority.

Different dimensions can be distinguished in the analysis of gender equality in education. UNESCO recommends the following Framework for achieving gender equality (Gender equality Framework):

- equality in education means creating equal opportunities for boys and girls to enter formal and informal education;
- equality in the educational process implies that boys and girls receive fair assessment and attention in the educational process, that is, they are engaged in the same educational programs, which are designed taking into account the acceptable differences associated with different methods of teaching boys and girls;
- equality in educational outcomes means that the grades of boys and girls in educational outcomes are based on their individual talents and efforts. In order to ensure fair opportunities for success, the duration of education, academic qualifications and diplomas cannot be differentiated based on gender;
- equality in external outcomes is the equal status of women and men in their ability to acquire goods and resources, to participate in economic, social, cultural and political activities and to contribute to benefits.

Currently, in the international experience, two different approaches to gender education are used in the higher education system:

- 1) providing special education on gender studies;
- 2) to incorporate knowledge about gender into the content of other educational lessons.

According to the first approach, gender issues are covered through special educational courses, such as "Gender Studies", "Feminist Studies", "Men's Studies", "Women's Studies", and then these courses are included as an independent discipline with an independent methodology.

According to the second approach, gender issues are included in the content of existing disciplines, such as sociology, history, pedagogy, jurisprudence, and other disciplines, in which case it becomes possible to identify and analyze the existing problems of gender inequality in various fields.

In the research of scientists from foreign and CIS countries issues of gender and gender approach in education to give boys and girls the same opportunities in education and ensure equality;

selection of forms, methods, and means of teaching that serve to fully realize their potential, based on the psychophysiological characteristics of boys and girls during the educational process;

directions such as ensuring gender tolerance, gender equality in the educational institution, as well as implementing gender analysis of the educational content, increasing the gender literacy of teachers have been scientifically and theoretically studied.

These approaches allow for complementary and planned mainstreaming of gender knowledge into higher education.

References:

1. Мирзиёев Ш. Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси. – Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон” нашриёти, 2021. – Б. 53.
2. Қурбонова Г.М. Гендер тенглик ва фарқлар асосида таълим бериш имкониятлари// Замонавий таълим. 2015, 12. – Б. 59-63.
3. Хоф Р. Возникновение и развитие гендерных исследований. / Пол, тендер, культу-ра. // Под ред. Э.Шопе и К. Хайдер. – М.: 1999. – С. 23-53.
4. Sobirjonovich S. I. et al. DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL GAMES FOR CHILDREN AGED 6-7 //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 1012-1018.
5. Tursunova, D. (2022). PRIORITY PRINCIPLES AND PJTIMO-PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN FEMALE STUDENTS. Science and Innovation, 1(3), 523-529.
6. Sobirjonovich S. I. et al. Using Innovative Technologies to Develop Creative Thinking //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 118-127.
7. Tursunova, D. (2022). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 285-289.
8. Soliev I. S. Factors of formation of information competence of future primary school teachers //Наука и просвещение: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации. – 2020. – С. 218-220.
9. Tursunova, D. (2021, December). THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 84-87).
10. Ergasheva D. et al. The role of primary education in the upbringing of the mature generation //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 139-141.